

'For ...Vs With...' Role of technology in Education And Skill Development of Intellectually Disabled

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Ever since the civilization has come to existence the society and community has treated disability as different. This conceptualization of "being different" may drive it notions from individualistic or collective approach. The individuals may either be "special" or may also be "differently able", if not "liability or burden" that is of no use to citizens, nations and even for family. But the fact that we create "others" in the name of disability and even in the name of inclusion is a reality that needs introspection more than investigation. Around the globe the rehabilitation and education for people living with disability has been institutionalized and is driven by collective intelligence of those who may not have been subjected to challenges that these "special" live with. Being judgemental is a by product of being literate that drive its tenants from knowledge that we accumulate as individuals and society. This intelligence of normal's gives a right to decide for those who may or may not take decisions for themselves. "Change" the basic law of nature does not come to them naturally, courtesy hierarchy of the intelligence of normal's over special need of "differently abled". Physical disability that may propose physical challenges, but the individuals and groups can demand what they think is

helpful for them. But impairment in mental and intellectual process takes away even that space from individuals living with mental retardation.

"Tatvam Asi Shwet Ketu" the idea that gives a sense of equality not by virtue of citizenship or constitutional authorities or welfare schemes, but by virtue of being human. No matter what percentage of population contribute to which type of disability, their right to education and rehabilitation should be focused on the needs of individual rather than their head counts. The changes in the society and institutional framework have been translated to these services but with what proposition? The study is an attempt to investigate one such domain that has come obviously to normalcy. Technology that influenced and made a deep impact in every domain of present day society has become an obvious phenomenon. We don't consider this as a special need or privileged service. Education and skill development has moves from mechanical and dynamics operations. Assistive devices are important for meeting challenges and have proven its significance for DAILY life. But services in the sector can play the role of a catalyst in improving the approach and adaptability of education when we talk of Intellectual disability. Is there a need to move forward from assistive devices to compatible services even for individuals living with mental retardation? The technology driven out of human and developmental needs and priorities proposed by MR and delivered by professionals, family, friends, institutions, community and state having a consent of the principle stakeholder i.e. client, called "TECHNOGOGY".

Historical Perspective

Some of the experts are of the opinion that everything that is not biological is technology. Chair is a technology, table is a technology, fan, pen, book etc all are technology. The best technology that has changed the lives of people living with profound and severe mental

retardation is the use of artificial respirator that has given an opportunity to move them out of institutional settings. Being alive with dignity is above any other need in human race. All other rights are subject to life (Victor Hugo).

The history has moved from social perception of being a creation of lesser God or a curse. It is important to focus on the studies that has contributed is more fruitful rather than fixing responsibilities for the unpleasant past. The problem of mental retardation has manifested itself in various forms over the past several decades; 2 percent of the population is retarded in mental and psychological development. These individuals have been treated in various ways: some have always been cared for and protected lovingly; others are looked at askance as noisome and useless mouths that must be fed; still others are given employment and assigned to simple jobs when business is good. Most of these individuals learn to walk, talk, and think rather late; they are intellectually and emotionally behind the others when the time comes to place them in kindergarten or school; in most cases, they leave school because they have had to repeat grades once or several times; or they become special cases, provided they are at all suited for school education. Today the need of technological intervention for rehabilitation services has moved from assistive mode to driving mode. The present study is a step forward in this direction.

Conceptual perspective Mental Retardation

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business is good. Most of these individuals learn to walk, talk, and think rather late; they are intellectually and emotionally behind the others when the time comes to place them in kindergarten or school; in most cases, they leave school because they have had to repeat grades once or several times; or they become special cases, provided they are at all suited for school education. Technology that has now both devices and service division can be an extension for rehabilitation for mental retardation. All across the globe especially in western world, professional are of the opinion that information technology and computational services has a larger role to play. India with it large population and limited professional working for mental health services, technology can be of significant support and outreach.

Research Methodology

To find the present status and future perspective a study with a sample size of 200 is conducted across Delhi NCR region. The research focuses on the use of technology for Education and Skill Development of Adolescents and Adults with mild and moderate level of retardation. Also a sample of 20 professionals working in the sector and family member are respondent. A descriptive method using questionnaires, Interview Schedule, case study, focus group discussions and non participatory observation has helped in collection of data. Sample selected is an outcome of random sampling technique and respondents are contacted personally. Both cluster sampling and snowball sampling are the important sampling techniques used. Special schools, inclusive education, training centres and rehabilitation services across Delhi are selected. The data collected, tabulated, analysed and processed. The description from interviews and case study does not speak for themselves.

In order to study the approach of the professionals and the significant others, the investigator used group discussions and

personal interaction with them. Other than the above mentioned tools; non participant observation was the most important tool. The data collected by using questionnaire is tabulated and analysed below.

Table 1
Analyses of Use of Technology by Professional and "Significant Others"

Professional Domain		N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD	Skewness		Kurtosis	
								Std. Error		Std. Error
Non Clinical Professionals	Total Tech for MR	14	6	32	21.43	7.013	-.659	.597	.232	1.154
	Total Tech with MR		0	8	2.07	2.464	1.776	.597	2.427	1.154
Clinical Professionals	Total Tech for MR	6	10	29	18.50	9.397	.074	.845	-3.124	1.741
	Total Tech with MR		0	10	3.17	3.764	1.528	.845	1.905	1.741

@For and with Individuals with MR

For Non-Clinical Professionals, Table 1 shows that the overall mean scores of use of technology 'for MR' that reflect the sector itself (21.43) is more than the mean score of use of technology 'with MR' (2.07). The scores lie in the middle border of "moderate category" of the means of overall score for the use of technology 'for MR' whereas the score lies in the lower border of "lower category" for use of technology 'with MR' in the same category. The Coefficients of skewness (-0.659) indicates an asymmetric distribution, with a longer tail towards left for technology 'for MR' and Coefficients of skewness (1.776) indicates an asymmetric distribution, with a longer tail towards right for technology 'with MR'. Whereas Coefficients of Kurtosis value for technology 'for MR' (0.232) indicates more peaks and Coefficients of Kurtosis value for technology 'with MR' (2.427) indicates more peaks.

For Clinical Professionals, Table 1 shows that the overall mean scores of use of technology

'for MR' that reflect the sector itself (18.50) is more than the mean score of use of technology 'with MR' (3.17). The scores lie in the middle border of "moderate category" of the means of overall score for the use of technology 'for MR' whereas the score lies in the lower border of "lower category" for use of technology 'with MR' in the same category. The Coefficients of

skewness (0.074) indicates an asymmetric distribution, with a longer tail towards right for technology 'for MR' and Coefficients of skewness (1.528) indicates an asymmetric distribution, with a longer tail towards right for technology 'with MR'. Whereas Coefficients of Kurtosis value for technology 'for MR' (-3.124) indicates flatter distribution more peaks and Coefficients of Kurtosis value for technology 'with MR' (1.905) indicates more peaks.

GRAPH 1

Distribution of overall score of Means and SD for Use of Technology by Professionals

Conclusion

The present study is a work of science and art as deals with human aspirations with the scientific acumen. The work does talks about the present status of technology in the education and skill development of MR specifically for mild and moderate. But it also underlines the fact that technology can play an important role for the same. The bigger question of affordability and control over the accessibility and adaptability has been the proposed by the investigator. The rationale of education and skill development are for psychosocial propositions that come naturally to all, but not to individuals living with mental retardation. Technology can be the torch that can make Dignity, Purpose, Control and Togetherness visible in the lives of MR, asserting the fountain of education and skills. Let accumulation of money and wisdom be for "others".

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